

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE PEDAGOGICAL APPROACH IN FORMING ECOTOURISM IN STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article provides information on the importance of the pedagogical approach in the formation of ecotourism in students

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All spheres of human life, be it family, work, everyday life, and other things, consist of mutual relationships. Nature is not only a sphere of human life, but also a living environment that changes as humanity adapts to itself. Thousands of years of labor, the struggle for their existence have led not only to the development and progress of civilization, but also to major changes in the environment. Throughout history, society has faced problems of an ecological nature. The emergence of man on Earth has led to his significant impact on the biosphere. The culture that created technocratic civilization has come into conflict with the laws of nature. In the conditions of industrial society and demographic explosion, the negative consequences of human activity have become global. Through consumption, human society has exceeded the ability of the biosphere to restore what has been lost. Modern society has come to realize the need for rational development and preservation of the living natural environment. The interaction of man with nature has led to the activities of naturalists and ecological

“Ecology” is a field of knowledge that covers the sphere of interaction between man and nature. The origins of this science are found in the Ancient World. The surviving drawings on stones left by primitive people are written evidence of a high interest of man in nature. Analysis of such images by modern science allows us to assess the behavior and appearance of animals in relation to the ecological problems of primitive people. The formation of ecological culture is a purposeful process of forming an ecological culture based on the knowledge of the laws of the functioning of ecological systems in each person, understanding the uniqueness of nature and human life, active protection of the environment, awareness of oneself as a part of nature, as well as the formation of readiness for it. The formation of ecological culture in the process of upbringing is associated with the formation of the most important qualities of a person (responsibility, humanity, citizenship), since only a comprehensively

developed person can create harmony in relations with the outside world. The result of ecological education can be assessed by the level of development of the ecological culture of a person, since this is the goal, the most important direction of ecological culture.

The formation of ecological culture is considered as a process of continuous education and development of a person, which is aimed at the formation of a system of values-oriented behavior and activity that ensures the development of scientific and practical knowledge and skills, a responsible attitude to the surrounding socio-natural environment and health.

The process of forming an ecological culture directs students to master social and ecological experience, prepares them for the best interaction with various types of activities related to environmental problems. Therefore, ecological culture is understood as a set of natural cultural systems, which is based on a set of knowledge about the laws of operation of natural systems, the ability to predict and foresee the consequences of human intervention in natural relations, and conscious compliance with them. Thus, the formation of an ecological culture of future engineers is a purposeful, multi-stage process aimed at educating an environmentally responsible person, who is distinguished by the ability to foresee the consequences of their actions and behavior, and can reduce their harmful impact on themselves and the natural environment. For this, it is necessary to carry out such psychological and pedagogical actions that, as a result, create pedagogical conditions that will affect the change in human needs and values. The formation of an ecological culture is a purposeful, systematic activity aimed at the development of the individual. Therefore, the preparation of future engineers for professional activity includes the formation of their ecological beliefs and the presence of a system of scientific knowledge and skills to form an ecological culture among students.

Ecological education, as an element of general education, is associated with the mastery of the scientific foundations of the interaction between nature and society. Its purpose is to form an ecological worldview, a system of knowledge, views, and beliefs aimed at educating a person's spiritual responsibility for the state of the environment, realizing the need for constant care for it in all types of activity. The interdisciplinary nature of ecological knowledge determines the nature of its impact on the entire educational system and affects all areas and aspects of education and upbringing. At the present stage of university education, the ecological culture of young people is being formed on the basis of the principles of the unity of historical relations between nature and society. The

multifaceted nature of the interaction between society and nature determines the complexity of ecological education, its main principles: an interdisciplinary approach to the formation of ecological culture, systematic and continuous study of educational material, the unity of intellectual and emotional-volitional principles. Students' activities in the study and improvement of the natural environment; the interrelation of global, regional and local historical environmental problems. This has been emphasized by many scientists. Based on the experience accumulated by science in studying this problem, we consider ecological culture as a set of scientific knowledge about the experience of the interaction of man and nature, historically formed in different cultural periods; the ability of a person to rationally and emotionally perceive the world around him and himself in it, readiness for environmental protection measures. This is a special personal education, which consists of the following elements: understanding the uniqueness and complexity of natural phenomena, their relationships; integrity of ecological knowledge; ability to think within the boundaries of ecological safety; compliance with the laws of environmental protection; the ability to create constructive moral rules regulating the relationship of man with his natural environment; readiness to take responsibility for environmental protection. The process of forming the ecological culture of university students is based on a scientific basis, covers most of the disciplines studied and pursues the following goals.

These goals can be expressed in the following groups of tasks: cognitive (mastery of basic scientific ecological concepts and facts); understanding the value of nature as a source of material and spiritual forces of society and each individual; motivational (development of society's needs for nature; conscious adherence to environmentally friendly norms of behavior); activity (activation of activities to protect the natural environment, participation in the promotion of nature conservation ideas). In our observations, the content of environmental education was selected in accordance with the main pedagogical principles: consistency and expediency; unity and differentiation of empirical and theoretical components, scientific and practical components; completeness of content within the time allotted for studying this discipline; continuity of content, taking into account the assimilation of previously obtained information; schematization and modeling; compliance of the content of the subject with the capabilities of the educational and material base of the educational institution, taking into account the prospects for its near future development. One more principle should be added to this list, without the implementation of which the

development of modern education will be impossible - the principle of cultural compatibility. This position is connected with the understanding that environmental problems should be considered taking into account ethnic identity. Since ecology is a science about home, homeland, the goal of modern environmental education is to approach the implementation of the idea of a national home by restoring the natural connections of man, nature. It is impossible to demonstrate the authenticity of humanity outside of culture. Reconstruction in education is carried out through integrated courses, bringing together natural and humanitarian sciences.

List of used literature:

1. Mashkova, I.V. The role of environmentalization of education in the education system / I.V. Mashkova // Materials of the scientific method. conf. / Young scientists of the Ural state. Physical University of culture. - Chelyabinsk, 2007. - P. 119-125.
2. Pedagogical science and education: thematic. Saturday. scientific. Publication. A.Ya. Nain / ChelGNOTS UpO RAO. - Chelyabinsk: 2004. - P. - 216.
4. Problems of formation of professional and ecological competence of the teacher in conditions of person-oriented education: materials of scientific method. conf. teachers. A.Ya. Flyer; VSPU. - Vladimir: 2007. - P. - 229.
5. Fortunatov, A.A. Methodological conditions for studying the problem of development of ecological culture of youth: textbook. Pension / Fortunatov A.A.; MaGU. - Magnitogorsk: 2009. -P.- 87.